

REGRESSIVE DISCONTINUANCE INTENTION: SCALE DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION

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ABSTRACT

Of late, research in the area of Discontinuance Intention (DI) is slowly gaining momentum. Notwithstanding such renewed interest, the DI construct seems to have been vaguely defined leaving ample scope for further elaboration. Lately, researchers have defined DI not simply being the opposite of Continuance Intention (CI). They argue that these two constructs are not polar opposites but may continue to remain at the same time in an individual. Also, systematic literature reviews in the area of DI have suggested that discontinuance can be of various types and forms and having one uniform scale may not be adequate. DI applies to a broad range of domains covering all hedonic and utilitarian consumption and has different forms and facets. Stating this reasoning and logic, researchers have pointed out the necessity to revisit the construct from wider perspectives. Unfortunately, not much attention has been given towards this line of thinking. Hence, a comprehensive definition of the construct and its various forms to conceptualize it afresh now becomes pertinent from the process, context, and content perspectives. With a conceptual review of 58 papers published during 2001 and 2021 in the areas of CI and DI, the present study aims to first do a literature review of discontinuance intention. Second, it aims to develop a scale for regressive DI among the five forms of Information System (IS) discontinuance, namely, **i) rejection, ii) regressive discontinuance, iii) Quitting, iv) Temporary discontinuance and v) Replacement** as coined by (Soliman & Rinta-Kahila, 2020). The current study while doing a conceptual review of the DI construct aims to provide a holistic perspective and draws on the imperative to consider 'intention' more than the actual 'act'/'action'. Finally, it aims to develop a reliable and valid scale for regressive DI which is expected to be the final outcome of the research study.

Among the five forms of IS discontinuance, regressive discontinuance intention suggests an intention to discontinue after accepting it initially. This is yet to be empirically validated by making use of a reliable scale. From purely an intention perspective, it may be even more important to focus on regressive discontinuance compared to rejection or replacement intentions as this covers the apprehensions about product or service after its initial use or adoption. Once the scale is developed, further research can be conducted to identify the predictors. The reasons for such apprehensions or concerns can be identified and timely measures can be taken by practitioners such that they don't result in replacement. This study aims to fill the void in the literature by developing a robust measure for the regressive discontinuance intention, a form of DI that is prevalent and could be of bigger concern to practitioners and academicians alike. Mixed-method design of data collection involving item generation, scale purification and its final validation by employing interview, content evaluation panel, pilot test will be carried out. Different forms of validity such as face validity, content validity, convergent validity, discriminant validity and reliability of the instrument.

PURPOSE/PROBLEM

Of late, research in the area of Discontinuance Intention (DI) is slowly gaining momentum. Notwithstanding such renewed interest, the DI construct seems to have been vaguely defined leaving ample scope for further elaboration. Discontinuance simply means the state of not using a product or service after initial adoption or use. It is important to study the phenomenon of discontinuance, from service provider perspectives, primarily for three reasons, viz, i) subscriber base and market share depends both on initial adopters and discontinuers, ii) negative interpersonal influencers are more persuasive than positive influencers in triggering discontinuance, iii) acquiring new customers is more expensive than retaining old ones (Parthasarathy & Bhattacharjee, 1998). Despite the need for discontinuance research being highlighted as early as the late 1990s, the majority of research in this domain has developed post-2010. Black (1983) also pointed out despite research on innovation and the diffusion of innovation starting early 1960s and 1970s, post-adoption decisions have not been given due attention. Similarly, Bhattacharjee (2001) pointed out how earlier research have not explained adequately psychological motivations of users after their initial acceptance that may influence their subsequent continuance decisions but not their prior acceptance decisions. This compounds the requirement to consider discontinuance as a potential post-adoption decision-one that is significant for the user, and as suggested above, for the provider.

Lately, researchers (Butcher et.al, 2020, Turel, 2014, Turel, 2016) have defined DI not simply being the opposite of Continuance Intention (CI). They argue that these two constructs are not polar opposites but may continue to remain at the

same time in an individual. Also, systematic literature reviews in the area of DI have suggested that discontinuance can be of various types and forms and having one uniform scale may not be adequate. DI applies to a broad range of domains covering all hedonic and utilitarian consumption and has different forms and facets. Stating this reasoning and logic, researchers have pointed out the necessity to revisit the construct from wider perspectives. Unfortunately, not much attention has been given towards this line of thinking. Hence, a comprehensive definition of the construct and its various forms to conceptualize it afresh now becomes pertinent from the process, context, and content perspectives. With a conceptual review of 58 papers published during 2001 and 2021 in the areas of CI and DI, the present study aims to first do a literature review of discontinuance intention. Second, it aims to develop a scale for regressive DI among the five forms of Information System (IS) discontinuance, namely, i) rejection, ii) regressive discontinuance, iii) Quitting, iv) Temporary discontinuance and v) Replacement as coined by (Soliman & Rinta-Kahila, 2020).

STUDY DESIGN/METHODOLOGY/APPROACH

This study adopts a mixed-method design wherein researcher aims to come up with an operational definition of the concept through exploratory methods and then the instrument validation. This follows a refinement of the construct used, namely, 'regressive discontinuance' with the already existing conceptualization by Soliman and Rinta-Kahila (2020) and Butcher et al (2020). The existing definition of IS regressive discontinuance has been in the context of Information Systems (IS) Discontinuance. Developing a scale for IS regressive discontinuance intention requires looking into the construct from the perspective of IS, and thus, there is a need to operationalize the construct.

Among different mixed-method designs, this study utilizes the two-phase, exploratory sequential design which involves Qualitative design followed by the Quantitative design. The basic tenet for using Qualitative Design followed by Quantitative Design is because the phenomenon is very less understood as regressive discontinuance has been coined by authors as late as in 2020, that too in the context of IS discontinuance. Given, that no standard instrument exists to measure this attitudinal variable called as Regressive Discontinuance Intention. Hence, the qualitative inquiry by means of conducting semi-structured interviews to explore the different facets of this construct, generate items based on literature review and interview. Items generated will be validated by checking it with experts, such as academicians and researchers. Quantitative approach will be applied for carrying out survey for empirical validation of the scale.

Semi-structured interviews will be conducted among participants, to generate better understanding of the attitudinal variable of regressive discontinuance intention based on the current definition by the authors. Purposive sampling will be used to

approach the subjects as the researcher would like to approach subjects who experience regressive discontinuance across all the domains in Information Systems ranging from social media, e-learning, utility apps such as productivity apps, mobile apps, mobile wallet, health apps, gaming apps, dating apps, music apps, entertainment apps, etc

Researcher conducted 30 semi-structured interviews, utilizing both online and offline platforms. In order to ensure diversity of the participants, researcher conducted online interviews. Final number of respondents for analysis will depend on information saturation. In-depth semi-structured interviews lasted for about 30-45 minutes' duration. Each subject was asked to read a consent form wherein s/he agreed to be interviewed. Permission for recording of the interview for ease of transcription was sought from the subjects beforehand. The identity of the respondents would be kept confidential during data transcribing and coding. Questions for semi-structured interview for all participants followed same format. The preliminary analysis from the interview will be shared in the colloquium in the form of codes and categories that are generated.

In the next phase of the study, quantitative study will be done following well-established scale development procedure by DeVellis, 2017. Content validation and initial purification of the items will be done by reaching out to expert judges (marketing professors and researchers in the area of consumer behaviors). Pilot testing will be done among 30 sample of respondents. Initial items of the questionnaires will be drafted such that only consumers who have experienced some kind of discontinuance intention are qualified to answer the questionnaires. Feedback from pilot study will be incorporated to the final questionnaire. Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) will be carried out to explore the underlying factors of the regressive discontinuance intention.

Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) using AMOS will be undertaken on the data to verify the dimensionality and reliability of the final set of questionnaire on regressive discontinuance intention. The CFA procedure will be carried out using IBM-SPSS- AMOS 24 with the Maximum Likelihood Estimator (MLE) algorithm. While EFA provides an indication of the structure of the construct, CFA is used to examine a proposed measurement model is desirable. To measure the measurement model, indices of model fit, model comparison, and model parsimony will be calculated (Dorman, 2003). Model fit indices include Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA), Goodness of Fit Index (GFI), Model comparison includes Tucker- Lewis Index (TLI), Relative Non-Centrality Index (RNI), Model Parsimony includes Parsimony Goodness of Fit Index (PGFI), Parsimony Normed Fit Index (PNFI).

Internal consistency reliability as the name implies, is concerned with the homogeneity of the items within the scale which is generally measured through

Cronbach alpha (DeVellis, 2017). Reliability of all the items of the construct regressive discontinuance intention will be measured. Validity such as construct validity, face validity, convergent validity will be computed.

FINDINGS

Content analysis of the data from qualitative interviews will be shared in the DC.

ORIGINALITY/VALUE

The current study draws on the imperative to consider '*intention*' more than the actual '*act*'/'*action*'. Finally, it aims to develop a reliable and valid scale for regressive DI which is expected to be developed as the final outcome of the research study. Among the five forms of IS discontinuance, regressive discontinuance intention suggests an intention to discontinue after accepting it initially. This is yet to be empirically validated by making use of a reliable scale. From purely an intention perspective, it may be even more important to focus on regressive discontinuance compared to rejection or replacement intentions as this covers the apprehensions about product or service after its initial use or adoption. The reasons for such apprehensions or concerns can be identified and timely measures can be taken by practitioners such that they don't result in replacement.

Continuance and discontinuance literature is rife with theories. Most of them borrow and rely on the foundational theories of adoption and discontinuance. However, it looks like the theories that predict pre-adoption intention and/ or resistance may be different from post-adoption intention and/ or resistance. All these multiple theories provide some insights regarding the approach, avoidance and ambivalence intention and state of use of social media, IS, e-learning, and several other use contexts such as food apps, gamification apps and so on. No conclusive evidence has yet been arrived as to which among these factors predict continuance and which factors predict discontinuance exclusively, or if the factors for continuance and discontinuance can co-exist at the same time period and context. As it appears, discontinuance may not be single point behavior. Thus, the intention to measure the construct should be viewed from a similar lens. For instance: Soliman and Rinta-Kahila (2020) classified continuance as consisting of several forms, such as sporadic use, routinization, habitual use, and excessive use. Likewise, they classified discontinuance as several forms, such as terminating usage, uninstalling, and deactivation. Currently, the scales measuring discontinuance intention does not cover these three forms of discontinuance. It is important to understand and empirically validate how these different forms of discontinuance are distinct especially in the context of IS discontinuance. IS discontinuance covers a broad range of discontinuance practices and thus narrowing the development of

the scale in the context of IS domain to be replicated in other domains later could be a useful outcome of this research.

The underlying theory that explains Regressive Discontinuance is Expectation Disconfirmation Theory by (Bhattacharjee, 2001 as cited by Soliman and Rinta-Kahila, 2020). It is important to understand and differentiate if the scales that measure regressive discontinuance are grounded on this theory and represent a special case of IS discontinuance.

RESEARCH LIMITATIONS/IMPLICATIONS

Limitation of the scale is that it is focused in the area of Information System, mainly on use of apps used in mobile devices. The scale has potential implications for managers as currently all forms of DI are considered as one. Since, rejecting an app, or deciding to postpone the use, is not similar to temporary discontinuance, it is important all these different forms of DI be treated differently. A specific scale in place of a generic one would be useful for understanding how different are these different forms of DI.

DISCUSSION/CONCLUSION

This study aims to fill the void in the literature by developing a robust measure for the regressive discontinuance intention, a form of DI that is prevalent and could be of bigger concern to practitioners and academicians alike. Further study can be conducted to develop scales for other four types of Discontinuance Intention.

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